

The problem of parameterization of auxiliary words in the database of the national corpus of the Uzbek language and providing them in the interface

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Abstract. The article provides theoretical knowledge about the provision of auxiliaries, connectives and predicates in the national corpus, scientific research on defining their categories, creating the interface of the auxiliaries, setting their parameters and placing them in the database of the national corpus of the Uzbek language. The author gave his scientific views on how to determine the parametrization of auxiliary words of the Uzbek language and how to use them to place them in the database.

Keywords: vocabulary, auxiliary vocabulary interface, corpus, linguistic database, transposition, modeling, syntactic framework, parameterization.

A.K. Borovkov, Sh. Shoabdurahmonov, T. Rustamov, A. Akhmedov were among the first to study auxiliaries in Uzbek linguistics, and G. Abdurahmonov, M. Askarova, A. Nurmonov, A. Berdialiyev at the syntactic level. A large-scale research has been done in linguistics on auxiliary words. For example, Z. Burkhanov "Pragmatics of auxiliaries and their functional agreements in Uzbek", A. Pardayev "The role of Uzbek auxiliary word groups in the linguistic system and linguopragmatic analysis", R. Rasulov "Uzbek semantic-grammatical features of auxiliary words in the language", A. Nurmonov "Presupposition of auxiliary constructions", N. Ernazarov "Synonymy of connecting conjunctions//Issues of grammatical construction of the Uzbek language", Z. Isakov "In the Uzbek language interrelation of word groups and the place of prepositions in it", U. Rahimov "Presupposition of prepositions in the Uzbek language", D. Urinboyeva "Words that do not change in Uzbek colloquial speech (auxiliary words)", T.Kh. Turdiboyev scientifically justified the function of auxiliary words at the morphological level in his research on the topic "Conversion of auxiliary words in the Uzbek language".

The current age of science and technology has taught us to find the easiest solution to problems in every process. This, in turn, was reflected in linguistic research. "Nowadays, with the help of the national language corpus, the creation of a wide range of opportunities for language users and learners, including linguists, lexicographers, computational linguists, editors, translators, journalists, publishers, scientists, teachers, learners and any other The fact that it is widely available to the specialist in the field to solve his language problems shows how important it is. [Mengliyev,2020:54]

In modern linguistics, many studies have been carried out on the Uzbek national corpus, which is an achievement of our national philology. For example, from Uzbek linguists Sh. Hamroyeva "Linguistic basis of creation of author corpus of Uzbek language", A. Eshmo'minov "Fundamentals of creation of synonym base of the national corpus of Uzbek language", D. Akhmedova "Opposition of Atov units" Linguistic bases and models of lexical-semantic tagging for Uzbek language corpora", O. Kholyirov, on the topic of "Linguistic bases of educational corpus of Uzbek language" on the topic of creating a database of Uzbek language and unifying it under a single source. achieved significant achievements.

The largest possible size of the language corpus determines the high point of the work in this regard. No matter how large the body is, its appearance is reflected in a very small window. Because a corpus is a miniature version of any language modelk oynada aks etadi. Chunki korpus har qanday til modelining kichraytirilgan ko‘rinishidir.[Zaxarov.2005:48] This window is called an interface. In today's work, we will talk about the corpus interface of auxiliary words in Uzbek, their linguistic transposition and parameterization.

Although auxiliaries have been scientifically studied by linguists, there are still problems in their parameterization and classification. That is, the fact that auxiliary words in Uzbek have an "intermediate third" feature between morphemes with lexical meaning and auxiliary morphemes

sometimes makes it difficult to study their content, and there are different scientific opinions about this in linguistics. Some linguists attribute auxiliary words to auxiliary morphemes, i.e. suffixes, some to parts of speech, and some to auxiliary words. This in itself makes it difficult to define the parameters of auxiliary words. [Sayfullayeva. 2010: 253]

In determining the transposition of the auxiliary word, the non-uniformity of scientific competences in linguistics creates a somewhat problematic situation in the expression of the word in the corpus. They are as follows:

- the auxiliary function of the verb |; (atab, deb, bo'ylab, deya, ko'ra, qarab, tortib, boshlab...)

Uzoqni ko'ra olish qobiliyati har kimda ham bo'lmaydi (independent verb)

Bundan ko'ra go'ng titganing yaxshi emasmi, qari tovuq (auxiliary)

Oyog'imdan tortib basharamgacha qonga bo'yaldim. (G`G`ulom) (auxiliary) Arqonni tortib bog'ladim.(independent verb)

- some locative nouns are used as auxiliaries with a noun in the base case, a possessive suffix of the third person, and the suffix of departure, place-time, departure agreement; (yon - yonida, yonidan, yoniga; ort- ortiga, ortida, ortidan; old- oldiga, oldida, oldidan; orqa - orqasiga, orqasida, orqasidan; ora- orasiga, orasida, orasidan; ust - ustiga, ustida, ustidan; ost - ostiga, ostida, ostidan; tag - tagiga, tagida, tagidan; qosh- qoshiga, qoshida, qoshidan; sifat-sifatida; bo'y-boyi; ko'y-kuyi; vaqt-vaqtida; tomon-tomoniga, tomonidan)

Yorning o'zi emas, bo'yi keldi.(noun)

Tun bo'yi beorom to'qiganim ul - tivit ro'mol emas, kechir, onajon.(auxiliary)

Kitob stolning ustida edi.(place noun)

Suhbat futbol ustida bo'ldi.(auxiliary).

When these words are auxiliary, they are mostly combined with nouns in the subject and the indicative. A.M. Scherbak, one of the pioneers of the comparative study of Turkic languages, without breaking the tradition in the grammar of modern Turkic languages, initially divides auxiliaries into two large groups: noun auxiliaries and verb auxiliaries. He defines this theory according to how the helper controls the words in the agreement. However, the Uzbek Turkic scholar Y. Abdurasulov does not fully agree with this opinion, and since such auxiliaries have preserved their original grammatical nature and characteristics related to action names, they are strictly between noun auxiliaries and verb auxiliaries. concludes that it is difficult to set limits. [Abdurasulov, 2009:199]

At this point, it is worth saying one thing that in the process of the grammaticalization of the assistant, the Turkic scholar gave some nouns that have changed or changed their meaning in the example of a number of auxiliary nouns, so we are full of this idea. We can't. For example, in the scientific views of Y. Abdurasulov *daraxtning bargida, daraxtning shoxida* in units like *shoxida, bargida* a classification is given that the words can be called either auxiliaries or nouns in place-time agreement. [Abdurasulov, 2009:200] In addition, the scientist classified the words of the ruler in such compounds as the mouth of the house and the foot of the mountain as auxiliaries.

- arrival of ravish as an assistant; (avval, oldin, ilgari, keyin, so'ng, tashqari, beri, gohida...)

Hamma ishlarimni bajarib bo'lganimdan keyin biroz dam oldim. (auxiliary)

Avval o'yla, keyin so'yla.(adverb)

- ravishning takrorlangan holatda bog'lovchi vazifasida kelishi; (sometimes)

Ba`zan Qoratoyning ishxonasida, ba`zan choyxonada tunab yurdi. (connective)

U ba`zan biznikiga kelib turadi. (adverb)

- that the number performs the function of a connector in the repeated case; (bir..., bir, birda..., birda)

Bir kulardi, bir yig'lardi.(bog'lovchi)

Bir savat oq gul (son)

- the occurrence of a modal word in the connecting function; (balki)

Bu voqea uning ruhiyatini tushirmadi, balki butunlay ishga sho'ng'ib ketdi.(connector)

Balki, ertaga o'ziga isitib berish uchun shunaqa deytgandir. (modal word)

- the appearance of the quality as a loading function; (*yolg'iz, tanho*)

Hamma keldi, yolg'iz sen yo'q eding (yuklama).

Yolg'iz farzandning yo'ldoshi Allohdir, bolam. (adjective)

- the appearance of the quality as an auxiliary; (*o'zga, boshqa*)

O'zingizni biling, o'zga bilan nima ishingiz bor. (sifat)

Bandamiz, taqdirga tan berishdan o'zga ilojimiz yo'q. (ko'makchi)

- in the basic case of the adjective, the third person takes the position of the possessive suffix and the suffix of place-tense as an auxiliary; (to'g'rida, to'g'risida; qarshi – qarshisida, qarshisida)

Sizning barcha fikrlaringiz to'g'ri. (adjective)

Bu to'g'rida ishimizning keyingi sahifasida fikr yuritimiz. (auxiliary)

- the occurrence of some words as homonyms in several different word groups and in auxiliary functions; (ortiq)

Har holda Toshkent aholisi Azizbek istibdodidan ortiq to'ydi, kimdan ko'mak so'rashni ham bilmaydi! (A.Qodiriy) (ravish)

O'ng qoshi ustidagi kichkina ortiq ham quruq qolmadi, qop-qora xol bo'lib, tiniq yuzda "mana men" deb o'z rassomini quvontirdi. (Oybek) (noun)

Shu eshitganingizdan ortiq hech narsa aytolmayman (auxiliary)

- Formativeness of 2nd person imperative verbs without person-number and tense suffixes (side, back...) with locative nouns and, in turn, the third person possessive suffix and departure of these nouns, sometimes, it comes in the role of auxiliary by bringing the suffix of the exit agreement; (yon - yoniga, yonida, yonidan; ort - ortiga, ortida, ortidan)

Yormat boshini ortga, xotini tomonga burib o'qraydi. (noun)

"Barcha yuklarni mashinaga ort", - deb buyurdi menga. (verb)

Muammoni hal qilish uchun bu ish ortidan ko'p yugurdi (auxiliary)

The occurrence of auxiliary words in the form of a lexical unit with the addition of -; (*birga*)

Shaharni birga aylandik (adverb)

Shu bilan birga har xil masalalarda Kozimjonning masalasini ham ko'ramiz. (an auxiliary)

When the preposition is added to nouns and prepositions -da, it also performs the function of place-time agreement;

Kaspiy dengizida paraxodlar qatnovi bahorga nisbatan ko'paydi. (Shuhrat) (adverb)

Hamma sabrning tagi ham oltin bo'lmas ekan-da, og'ayni! (yuklama)

- auxiliary morphemes of some similes and comparisons; (-dek, -day, -cha)

Po'latdek (kabi) dadil bir yigit bu ishdan hayiqsa, uyat bo'ladi. (O.Mux.)

It should be noted at this point that in formal linguistics there are interpretations that the suffixes -dek, -day, -cha do not have an auxiliary character, but are only word-formers and diminutives. From scientific point of view -dek, -day, -cha connectors *kabi, singari* should be considered auxiliary only when it can be used interchangeably with words. For example, *Nozimaning bir yigitcha (kabi) ishlashi hammani hayratga soldi*, in the sentence as -dek suffix, if we replace it with an auxiliary, it does not affect the general content. So, in this sentence suffix -cha comes as an auxiliary. *Bu yigitcha har kuni kutubxonaga qatnaydi*. In this sentence in the part of the word *yigitcha* suffix -cha means *kabi, singasi(as)*. So, in another sentence the suffix is not an auxiliary but it's a type of noun which means smaller.

-day that the auxiliary pronouns such as such, such, such, such, such, allakanday, such as *jinday, qittay, arziguday, say, jojahirday, olguday, davangirday* are rounded up, hardened and inseparable from the root; [Sayfullayeva, 2010:260]

Bu kunlarda uning qalami shunday g'avg'o ko'tardiki, Hirotda qayerga qarasangiz, Sultonali haqida eshitasiz. (Oybek)

Keksagina bir odam yelkasiga davangirday bir yigitni mindiribdi. (X.To'xtaboyev)

Auxiliary words in the Uzbek language are divided into the following types according to their form:

1. Pure assistants
2. Relative auxiliary words

3. Adverbial auxiliaries

[Sayfullayeva, 2010:256]

The occurrence of morphemes related to other word groups that we mentioned above in the function of auxiliary words is included in the list of relative auxiliaries. Because sometimes they come as an independent lexeme expressing a clear concept. Pure assistants do not have this feature. We called these words substantial (invariant) auxiliaries. That is, although it expresses a different meaningful relationship between sentences and words, it does not represent a specific concept and is interpreted as an auxiliary word regardless of its syntactic context. These are:

- *kabi, sari, sayin, singari, uzra, qadar, uchun, haqida, tufayli, orqali* (**auxiliaries**);

- *va, ammo, bilan, biroq, lekin, agar, agarda, garchi, ya'ni, toki, hamda, yo, yoki, yoxud, goh, chunki* (**connectors**);

- *hatto, hattoki, -mi, -chi, -a, -ya, -ku, xuddi, naq* (**downloads**).

Although auxiliary morphemes are formally auxiliary morphemes, they are accepted as words, and they are conditionally considered as word groups. These are: *-dek, -day, -cha* (**auxiliaries**)

-mi, -chi, -a, -ya, -gina (-kina, -qina) -oq, -yoq, -u, -yu, -da, -ov, -ki, -ku (**downloads**)

Including this type of assistants in the corps also creates some problems. Because such a word in the adverbial form is found in all three auxiliary structures. Although the adverbial form of conjunctions is not shown above, adverbial prepositions sometimes function as conjunctions. This is manifested in the following cases: *-u, -yu, -da yuklamalari ba'zi o'rinlarda bog'lovchi vazifasini bajaradi*;

- *mi yuklamasi takror holda kelib bog'lovchi vazifasida keladi*;

- *ki, -ku loads come as a binder.*

Quyosh chiqdi-da, (va) havo isidi. (-da load is used as an attachment link);

Quyosh chiqdi-yu(ammo), havo isimadi (-yu the load came in the function of a conflict binder);

Shunday yomg'ir yog'diki, ariqlarda suv sel bo'lib oqdi. (-ki yuklamasi ergashgan qo'shma gap qismlarini bog'lovchi vosita bo'lib kelgan)

Dadam keldilarmi, bolalarning hammasi ko'chag otildi. (here loader -mi is used as a causative link)

Corpora based on the analysis of large volumes of texts help us to define the category of helpers above. The parametrization of these words, that is, their functional functions, are determined depending on the function they perform in the text. When modeling them and creating an interface, an algorithm is created depending on which words are included in the syntactic circle. For example, when determining a helper, its following algorithm can be given:

noun+auxiliary+verb

adjective+auxiliary+verb

adjective+auxiliary+verb

action name+auxiliary+verb

number+auxiliary+verb

Bu algoritm yana quyidagi formula bilan mukammallashtirishi mumkin:

qaratqich kelishigidagi ot + ko'makchi+fe'l

bosh kelishikdagi ot + ko'makchi+fe'l

jo'nalish kelishigidagi ot + ko'makchi+fe'l

chiqish kelishigidagi ot+ ko'makchi+fe'l

jo'nalish kelishigidagi olmosh + ko'makchi+fe'l

In our further work, we planned to compile modeled tables for each auxiliary word based on the above scientific theories.

The first step in our approach to the corpus is its interface. The interface is a shell window. An interface is defined by its creator based on its purpose. It is like a mirror that we look at ourselves, that can clearly show our face. The more clear and high-quality the mirror is, the more accurately it reflects the person. As a mirror, the interface is also the best source for predicting what information is available. So, the more perfectly designed the interface of a given theme is, the easier it is for the

user. “Interfeys” Its entry into our vocabulary as an English word is due to the widespread use of personal computers and computer science courses in the mid-90s. The term is vague, but each of its specific meanings refers to different ways of human-computer interaction. An interface is a set of tools that allow the user to control all the functions of a computer.[8.http] Now this word is used by representatives of all fields that work with computers. In linguistics, the corpus interface allows the researcher to get the maximum amount of information from the computer.

At the interface of auxiliaries, different styles of texts help us to show that the lemma performs two different functions in the case of a single grammatical unit, as noted above. That is, in such a case, we determine the category of a word or unit in the form of an adverb depending on what words it is connected with in the syntactic circle. The use of the corpus method in the analysis of the possibility of lexical-semantic combination not only of auxiliary words, but also of all words makes it possible to create new generation dictionaries, grammars, in particular, a dictionary of stable combinations. [Zaxarova,2011;161] Observing the environment of one or another linguistic unit in the corpus, it is possible to determine certain semantic features characterizing this unit. A word can belong to several semantic categories at the same time, so it is necessary to think according to the degree of belonging of the word to one or another category. The level is determined by counting the frequency of distribution in different categories. [Muxin, 2010;174] Taking into account these aspects, the interface window of the corpus of auxiliary words can be given as follows:

1- table

<u>Bilan</u>		Paradigm of association with other words	
Category	Helper	Independent words that are not verbs in the main conjugation + <i>bilan</i> + fe’l Qalam bilan chizmoq; sen bilan bahslashmoq;	
It is used as another word group	As a connector	Independent words without verbs + independent words without verbs Men bilan onam; qalam bilan ruchka; oldi bilan orqasi...	
Meaningful	Not available	Ethymology	In old Turkish language as a form of - <i>ila, birla, birlan</i> ; in dialect as a form of <i>minan</i>
Variants	-la, ila, birla, birlan, minan.	In the meaning of loading	It means the manner of action, state, togetherness, cooperation, means. <i>Hassa bilan ochmoq (means) zavq bilan o’qimoq (mood) onam bilan bormoq (togetherness)</i>

Since the interface gives the first impression of the body and is the starting point of its use, its design requires a lot of responsibility from the author. The different design and structure of the interface of existing authoring bodies requires a unique aesthetic from the perfect interface body builder. Representation of the national color in the general view of the interface, the photo of the author, decorations reflecting the national color in the background, and the presence of classic or modern signs are important factors that ensure nationalism and originality in the corpus..[Hamroyeva,2020;108]

In conclusion, it can be said that although auxiliary words in the Uzbek language have been studied on a very large scale, thorough research has not yet been done on their inclusion in the national corpus. Therefore, in determining their parameters, the use of artistic, journalistic, official, scientific and colloquial style texts, in which the categories of auxiliary, connecting and predicates included in the Uzbek language database are clearly expressed, will help. In our further work, we aimed to model the transposition function of auxiliary words in the syntactic environment.

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